

Balkan Vegetation Database (BVD) – updated information and current status

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Abstract

The Balkan Vegetation Database (BVD; GIVD ID: EU-00-019) is a regional database, which was established in 2014. It comprises phytosociological relevés covering various vegetation types from nine countries of the Balkan Peninsula (Albania – 153 relevés, Bosnia and Herzegovina – 1715, Bulgaria – 12,282, Greece – 465, Croatia – 69, Kosovo – 493,

Montenegro – 440, North Macedonia – 13 and Serbia – 2677). Currently, it contains 18,306 relevés (compared to 9,580 in 2016), and most of them (82.8%) are geo-referenced. The database includes both digitized relevés from the literature (65.6%) and unpublished data (34.5%). Plot size is available for 84.7% of all relevés. During the last four years some “header data information” was improved e.g. elevation (now available for 83.4% of all relevés), aspect (67.7%), slope (66%), total cover of vegetation (54.3%), cover of tree, shrub, herb, bryophyte and lichen layers (27.1%, 20.1%, 40.2%, 11.5% and 2.1%), respectively. Data access is either semi-restricted (65.6%) or restricted (34.4%). Most relevés (84.6%) are classified to syntaxa of different levels. The database has been used for numerous studies with various objectives from floristic, vegetation and habitat-related topics, to macroecological studies at the local, regional, national, continental and global levels. During the last four years, BVD data were requested from 111 different projects via the EVA and sPlot databases.

Keywords

Balkan Peninsula, Balkan vegetation, conservation, TURBOVEG, vegetation plot, vegetation classification

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: EU-00-019		Last update: 2020-11-24	
Balkan Vegetation Database		Web address:	
Database manager(s): Kiril Vassilev (kiril5914@abv.bg); Hristo Pedashenko (hristo_pedashenko@yahoo.com)			
Owner: Kiril Vassilev, Hristo Pedashenko, Alexandra Alexandrova, Alexander Tashev, Anna Ganeva, Anna Gavrilova, Armin Macanović, Assen Assenov, Antonina Vitkova, Beloslava Genova, Borislav Grigorov, Chavdar Gushev, Ermin Mašić, Eva Filipova, Ganna Gecheva, Ina Aneva, Ilona Knollová, Ivaylo Nikolov, Georgi Georgiev, Georgi Gogushev, Georgi Tinchev, Ivan Minkov, Kalina Pachedzieva, Katerina Mincheva, Koycho Koev, Mariyana Lubenova, Marius Dimitrov, Media Gumus, Momchil Nazarov, Nadezhda Apostolova-Stoyanova, Nikolay Nikolov, Nikolay Velev, Petar Zhelev, Plamen Glogov, Rayna Natcheva, Rossen Tzonev, Senka Barudanović, Sofia Kostadinova, Steffen Boch, Stephan Hennekens, Stoyan Georgiev, Stoyan Stoyanov, Todor Karakiev, Tijana Ilić, Veronika Kalníková, Veselin Shivarov, Vladimir Vulchev			
Scope: Balkan Vegetation Database includes 18,306 relevés i.e. all vegetation types are considered, except the dry grasslands (which are in the Balkan Dry Grassland Database) from 9 Balkan countries (Albania – 153 relevés, Bosnia and Herzegovina - 1715, Bulgaria – 12,282, Greece – 465, Croatia – 69, Kosovo - 493, Montenegro – 440, North Macedonia – 13 and Serbia - 2677).			
Abstract:			
Availability: according to a specific agreement		Online upload: yes	Online search: yes
Database format(s): TURBOVEG		Export format(s): TURBOVEG	
Plot type(s): normal plots		Plot-size range: 0.2 to 8000	
Non-overlapping plots: 18307	Estimate of existing plots: 18307	Completeness: 100%	Status: completed and continuing
Total no. of plot observations: 18307	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 340		Valid taxa: 09573
Countries (%): BG: 67.09; RS: 14.62; KO: 2.69; ME: 2.40; AL: 0.84; BA: 9.37; GR: 2.54; HR: 0.38; MK: 0.07			
Formations: Forest: 29% // Non Forest: 71% = Aquatic: 4%; Terrestrial: 66%			
Guilds: all vascular plants: 100%; bryophytes (terricolous or aquatic): 16%; lichens (terricolous or aquatic): 7%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 83.4; slope aspect: 67.7; slope inclination: 66; other soil attributes: 0.6; soil pH: 0.02; land use categories: 11.21; soil depth: 17			
Performance measure(s): presence/absence only: 0%; cover: 100%; number of individuals: 0%; measurements like diameter or height of trees: 10.19%; biomass: 0%; other: 0%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 22.71%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 4.03%; small grid (not coarser than 10 km): 41.31%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 14.75%			
Sampling periods: before 1920: 0.01%; 1920-1929: 0.58%; 1930-1939: 0.32%; 1940-1949: 2.16%; 1950-1959: 14.91%; 1960-1969: 8.20%; 1970-1979: 7.22%; 1980-1989: 6.43%; 1990-1999: 14.29%; 2000-2009: 14.87%; 2010-2019: 27.15%; unknown: 3.86%			
Information as of 2020-11-24 further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/EU-00-019			

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